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Involvement of G protein-coupled receptor kinase 2 (GRK2) in the development of Non-Alcoholic Steatosis and Steatohepatitis in mice and humans.

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ABSTRACT

INSULIN RESISTANCE (IR) AND OBESITY ARE IMPORTANT RISK FACTORS FOR NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE (NAFLD). G PROTEIN-COUPLED RECEPTOR KINASE 2 (GRK2) IS INVOLVED IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF IR AND OBESITY *IN VIVO*. HOWEVER, ITS POSSIBLE CONTRIBUTION TO NAFLD AND/OR NON-ALCOHOLIC STEATOHEPATITIS (NASH) INDEPENDENTLY OF ITS ROLE ON IR OR FAT MASS ACCRETION HAS NOT BEEN EXPLORED. HERE, WE USED WILD-TYPE (WT) OR GRK2 HEMIZYGOUS (GRK2+/-) MICE FED A HIGH-FAT DIET (HFD) OR A METHIONINE AND CHOLINE-DEFICIENT DIET (MCD) AS A MODEL OF NASH INDEPENDENT OF ADIPOSITY AND IR. GRK2+/- MICE WERE PROTECTED FROM HFD-INDUCED NAFLD. MOREOVER, MCD FEEDING CAUSED AN INCREASED IN TRIGLYCERIDE CONTENT AND LIVER-TO-BODY WEIGHT RATIO IN WT MICE, FEATURES THAT WERE ATTENUATED IN GRK2+/- MICE. ACCORDING TO THEIR NAFLD ACTIVITY SCORE, MCD-FED GRK2+/- MICE WERE DIAGNOSED WITH SIMPLE STEATOSIS AND NOT OVERT NASH. THEY ALSO SHOWED REDUCED EXPRESSION OF LIPOGENIC AND LIPID-UPTAKE MARKERS AND LESS SIGNS OF INFLAMMATION IN THE LIVER. GRK2+/- MICE PRESERVED HEPATIC PROTECTIVE MECHANISMS AS ENHANCED AUTOPHAGY AND MITOCHONDRIAL FUSION AND BIOGENESIS, TOGETHER WITH REDUCED ENDOPLASMIC RETICULUM STRESS. GRK2 PROTEIN WAS INCREASED IN MCD-FED WT BUT NOT IN GRK2+/- MICE, AND ENHANCED GRK2 EXPRESSION POTENTIATED PALMITIC ACID-TRIGGERED LIPID ACCUMULATION IN HUMAN HEPATOCYTES DIRECTLY RELATING GRK2 LEVELS TO STEATOSIS. GRK2 PROTEIN AND MRNA LEVELS WERE INCREASED IN HUMAN LIVER BIOPSIES FROM SIMPLE STEATOSIS OR

NASH PATIENTS IN TWO DIFFERENT HUMAN COHORTS. OUR RESULTS DESCRIBE A FUNCTIONAL RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN GRK2 LEVELS AND HEPATIC LIPID ACCUMULATION AND IMPLICATE GRK2 IN THE ESTABLISHMENT AND/OR DEVELOPMENT OF NASH.

Keywords: GRK2, NAFLD, NASH, MCD, hepatic steatosis, NAS.

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Reduced GRK2 levels in GRK2^{+/-} mice protect from diet-induced NASH
- MCD-fed GRK2^{+/-} mice show less inflammation and ER stress markers in the liver
- GRK2^{+/-} mice preserve autophagy, mitochondrial dynamics and better lipid handling
- Hepatic GRK2 levels are increased in mice and humans with steatosis or NASH
- GRK2 over-expression potentiates lipid accumulation in human hepatic cells

Conflicts of interest: the authors declare they have no conflicts of interest to be declared.

List of Abbreviations: NAFLD, Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease; NASH, Non-alcoholic steatohepatitis; GRK2, G protein-coupled receptor kinase 2; GPCR: G protein-coupled receptor; T2D, type 2 diabetes; IR, Insulin resistance; HFD, High fat diet; ER, Endoplasmic reticulum; CD, Control diet; MCD, methionine and choline-deficient diet; NAS, NAFLD activity score; FAS: Fatty acid synthase; MAPK, Mitogen-activated protein kinase.

1. INTRODUCTION

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), defined as the accumulation of triglycerides (TG) in the liver in the absence of excessive alcohol consumption, is an extremely prevalent chronic liver disease worldwide, affecting about one quarter of adults in the developed countries [1]. NAFLD encompasses a spectrum of liver pathologies including simple steatosis that can progress to non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), fibrosis, cirrhosis and, finally, hepatocellular carcinoma. NASH is defined as the coexistence of hepatic steatosis with inflammation and hepatocyte injury, and involves

a variety of cellular responses such as endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress, impairment of autophagy and mitochondrial dysfunction. Contrary to most cases of simple steatosis, NASH has the potential of progressing to more advanced stages of liver disease [2].

The lipid accumulation that defines NAFLD disturbs the function of the ER in hepatocytes, thereby generating chronic ER stress that interferes with the normal cellular function [3]. Different stress-response mechanisms are subsequently activated in order to alleviate ER stress, including autophagy. Autophagy plays a protective role against NAFLD [4], but it is unable to resolve chronic stress during NASH resulting in an impaired autophagic flux, a key feature of NASH [5]. Moreover, autophagy can directly regulate steatosis by removing lipid droplets that are then transformed into fatty acids (FA) through lipophagy [6]. FA are usually catabolized via β -oxidation in the mitochondria, organelles able to increase in mass in a process known as mitochondrial biogenesis and change morphology by fission and fusion events. Alterations in these mitochondrial processes have been suggested to participate in the progression of NAFLD [7].

G protein-coupled receptor kinase 2 (GRK2) is a Serine/Threonine kinase classically known for its role in the regulation of G protein-coupled receptors (GPCRs). This protein also phosphorylates a variety of substrates and interacts with other targets in a kinase activity-independent manner [8]. Some of these targets are components of the insulin receptor cascade where GRK2 behaves as a negative regulator of insulin signaling [9]. Insulin resistance (IR) is defined as an impairment of the response of tissues to physiological insulin concentrations, and, together with obesity, are two well-established pathogenic factors associated to NAFLD. In fact, NAFLD is a very common condition among patients with type 2 diabetes (T2D) [10] whereas the development of NAFLD might also predispose individuals towards IR. Different pathologies including cardiovascular diseases and cancer show altered dosage or activity of GRK2 in certain tissues, suggesting that GRK2 levels may have considerable pathophysiological relevance [11, 12]. Interestingly, GRK2 levels are increased in murine models of IR and in human samples from insulin-resistant patients. Conversely, lowering GRK2 levels, as in GRK2 heterozygous (GRK2^{+/-}) mice, prevents the development of diet-induced IR and obesity, and the genetically induced downregulation of GRK2 is able to revert an already established obese and insulin-resistant phenotype [13-15]. Notably, tamoxifen-induced GRK2-deficient homozygous mice are also protected against high fat diet (HFD)-induced increase in hepatic lipid content and display decreased expression of pro-inflammatory markers in the liver [14]. However, whether this outcome in liver phenotype is solely a consequence of the overall effect of GRK2 dosage in systemic lipid management and insulin signaling remains to be addressed.

To investigate a possible effect of GRK2 in the development or progression of NASH independently from systemic IR and obesity we used the methionine and choline-deficient diet (MCD), a nutritional rodent model that reproduces key features of human NASH, in either wild-type or GRK2-hemizygous mice. Methionine and choline are essential for liver beta-oxidation and VLDL (very low density lipoproteins) production, and their deficiency results in hepatic steatosis, inflammation and fibrosis [16, 17]. Unlike the HFD, the MCD induces weight loss and mice do not become overtly insulin-resistant, displaying decreased levels of glucose and TG [18]. This fact allows for an analysis of the contribution of GRK2 to NASH independently from its effects on adiposity and IR, whereas the use of GRK2-hemizygous mice provides a model that would mimic the effect of a potential global pharmacological inhibitor for GRK2. We report herein that GRK2 downregulation can alleviate the development of NASH in non-obese mice by modifying the cellular processes involved in the progression of this condition. In addition, we show for the first time that GRK2 overexpression can *per se* increase steatosis in human hepatic cells and that hepatic GRK2 levels are increased during NASH in mice and humans.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Animal Protocols

Experiments were performed using male wild-type (WT) mice and mice hemizygous for GRK2 (GRK2^{+/-}) maintained on the C57BL/6 background and housed on a 12-hour light/dark cycle. 8-weeks old animals were fed *ad libitum* either a standard diet (SD, providing 13% of total calories from fat, 67% from carbohydrate and 20% from protein; 2014S Rodent Maintenance Diet, Teklad, Harlan, IN, USA) or a HFD (45% of total calories from fat, 35% from carbohydrate and 20% from protein, Rodent Diet D12451, Research Diets) for 12 weeks. For the MCD experimental model, 4 months-old GRK2^{+/-} and WT mice were fed either MCD diet (TD.90262 E1553-94, ENVIGO) or the corresponding control diet (CD, TD.90262 E15654-04, ENVIGO, NJ, USA) for 4 weeks. *db/+* and *db/db* mice in the C57BL/KsJ genetic background were purchased from Charles River Laboratories (Charles River, MA, USA). Animals were maintained at a temperature of 22±2 °C with a relative humidity of 50±10% and under pathogen-free conditions. Body weight was measured at the end of the experiment. For adenoviral overexpression experiments, 100µl of 5x10¹⁰ pfu/ml GRK2-containing Ad5 adenoviral constructs (described in [19]) or control cre-expressing virus (University of Iowa Viral Vector Core Facility, USA) were injected intravenously via the tail vein in 7 weeks-old C57BL/6 male animals (Charles River, MA, USA). Mice were sacrificed 23 days later.

All animal experimentation procedures conformed to the European Guidelines for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals (Directive 86/609) and were approved by the Ethical Committees for Animal Experimentation of our University and the Comunidad Autónoma de Madrid, Spain.

2.2 Human Samples

H&E and Masson's trichrome-stained paraffin-embedded liver biopsy sections were evaluated by an expert hepatopathologist who was unaware of the clinical data. Hepatic histopathological analysis was performed as described above, and according to the scoring system of Kleiner et al. [20]. Biopsies without steatosis and with few or without inflammatory cells or ballooned hepatocytes were considered as normal liver (NL). Simple steatosis (SS) was defined as the presence of at least 5% of steatotic hepatocytes with or without mild lobular or portal inflammation but in the absence of features of hepatocellular injury (ballooning, apoptosis or necrosis) and significant fibrosis. On the other hand, minimal criteria for the histological diagnosis of definite NASH included the combined presence of grade 1 steatosis, hepatocellular injury and lobular inflammation with or without fibrosis [21].

Cohort 1: Liver samples come from 41 patients with a clinical diagnosis of NAFLD (31 with simple steatosis, SS, and 11 with NASH) who underwent a liver biopsy by a percutaneous route during programmed cholecystectomy in Santa Cristina University Hospital (Madrid, Spain). Inclusion criteria for NAFLD patients were based on the absence of alcohol intake (<20 g/day), the presence of biopsy-proven steatosis with/without necroinflammation and/or fibrosis, and no evidence of hepatitis B and/or C virus (HBV and/or HCV, respectively) or human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infections. Patients with other causes of chronic liver disease or those receiving potentially hepatotoxic drugs were excluded. We further studied 34 patients to whom a liver biopsy was taken during programmed laparoscopic cholecystectomy and were diagnosed with histologically normal livers (NL). All the NL patients had normal fasting glucose, cholesterol and TG, normal serum ALT levels, and negative anti-HBV, anti-HCV, and anti-HIV tests. In addition, NL patients drank less than 20 g of alcohol per day and none used potentially hepatotoxic drugs.

Cohort 2: Liver samples come from healthy non-obese organ-transplant donors without liver lesions (NL) (n=5) as well as from 26 well-characterized obese NAFLD patients subjected to bariatric surgery in Valdecilla Hospital (Santander, Spain). Within obese patients, 3 presented normal liver histology (NL), 11 showed simple steatosis (SS) and 12 NASH. Inclusion criteria were as for Cohort 1 together with absence of inborn errors of metabolism, Wilson's disease, autoimmune hepatitis or cholestatic liver disease.

Both studies were performed in agreement with the Declaration of Helsinki, and with local and national laws. No donor organs were obtained from executed prisoners or other institutionalized persons. The Institutions' Human Ethics Committee approved the study procedures, and written informed consent was obtained from all patients before inclusion in the study.

2.3 Cell culture, infection and treatments

The human hepatocellular carcinoma cell line Huh7 was cultured in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% FBS. Cells were infected with 100 M.O.I. of either an adenovirus carrying the sequence of bovine GRK2, a sh-GRK2 construct for human GRK2 or control adenovirus as previously described [19]. Medium was replaced after 16 hours of infection.

To induce intracellular lipid accumulation in Huh7 cells, palmitic acid (Sigma–Aldrich, MO, USA) was dissolved to a 160 mM concentration in isopropyl alcohol and added to DMEM containing 1% fatty acid free BSA to obtain a physiological ratio between bound and unbound FA in the media [22]. The final palmitic acid concentration (500 μ M) is similar to the fasting total FFA plasma concentrations observed in humans with NASH [23]. Huh7 cells were plated in 6-well dishes and incubated for 24 h with palmitic acid-BSA complexes, using fatty acid-free BSA as a control.

2.4 Isolation and culture of primary murine hepatocytes and Kupffer cells

Hepatocytes were isolated from male WT mice fed either CD or MCD and from *db/+* or *db/db* mice by perfusion through the inferior cava vein with Hank's balanced salt solution (HBSS) (Gibco, MA, USA), 1 mM HEPES pH 7.4, 0.2 mM EGTA and William's E medium (Sigma-Aldrich, MO, USA) with 0.8 mg/ml collagenase type 1 (WorthingtonBiochemical Corporation, NJ, USA) [24]. After filtering through a cell strainer (100 μ m) and centrifugation at 70 g at 4 °C for 5 min, cells were resuspended in the following culture attachment medium: DMEM/F12, 20 mM HEPES pH 7.4, 0.05% NaHCO₃, 5 mM glucose, 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), 5 mg/ml BSA, 100 U/ml penicillin, 100 μ g/ml streptomycin and 50 μ g/ml gentamicin, and purified by density gradient centrifugation using an isotonic solution of Percoll (GE Healthcare Bio-Sciences AB, Uppsala, Sweden). After 2 washes, cells were plated in attachment medium in 6-well dishes for subsequent studies. For Kupffer cells isolation, the supernatant from the first centrifugation of the hepatocyte isolation protocol was collected and centrifuged twice at 50 g for 5 min to discard the pellet with remaining hepatocytes, as described previously [25]. Briefly, the resulting supernatant was centrifuged at 500 g for 5 min at 4 °C and the pellet containing the Kupffer cells was resuspended in the culture attachment medium. Cells were mixed by inversion with 50% Percoll and centrifuged at 1059 g for 30 min without brake at room temperature. Finally, the cell pellet was washed with PBS, centrifuged twice at 500 g for 10

min at 4 °C to wash out the residual Percoll solution and plated on dishes in attachment cultured medium with 10% FBS.

2.5 Western Blot analysis and Liver triglycerides content determination

Murine tissues were homogenized using metal beads in a Tissue Lyser (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) as previously described [26], and cells were lysed in RIPA lysis buffer. Proteins were resolved by SDS-PAGE, blotted and probed with the specific antibodies compiled in Supplementary Table 1. The amount of TG in the liver was measured by isopropanol extraction and the Serum Triglycerides Determination Kit (Sigma-Aldrich, MO, USA). See more details in Supplementary Materials.

2.6 Histochemistry

Mouse liver tissue sections were de-paraffinized and rehydrated prior to staining with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) according to standard procedures. For immunohistochemical detection of the F4/80 macrophage marker, slides were incubated overnight with the primary antibody anti-F4/80 (clone BM8, Abcam, Cambridge, UK) and detection was performed as described [27]. A negative control in the absence of the primary antibody was used. The presence of macrophages (F4/80-stained area) was determined using image analysis software (ImageJ). Three to five representative high-magnification fields from each section were analyzed per animal. Images were taken with an Olympus IX51 microscope.

Immunohistochemistry of paraffin sections of formalin-fixed human liver samples for the detection of GRK2 using the anti-GRK2 PF2 antibody [19] was performed as described [28]. Human liver tissue sections were de-paraffinized and rehydrated prior to staining and then samples were unmasked with TRIS pH 10 20 minutes at 97°C and were incubated overnight at 4°C with a 1:750 dilution of the primary antibody. Detection was performed with VECTOR VIP substrate (purple). A negative control in the absence of the primary antibody was used. The presence of GRK2-stained area was determined using Cell Profiler software (<http://cellprofiler.org/>). Five representative 40x magnification fields from each section were analyzed per animal. Images were taken with a Zeiss Axioimager microscope.

For Oil Red O staining, OCT frozen liver sections were stained with Oil red O as described [29] and mounted on 10% glycerol in PBS-DAPI (5ng/μl) to visualize the nucleus. All sections were examined using Fluorescence Resonance Energy Transfer (FRET) equipment coupled to an inverted Axiovert200 (Zeiss) microscope in the CBMSO Confocal Microscopy Facility. Oil red O-stained sections were examined in epifluorescence using a DsRed (500–650 nm) and DAPI (359-371 nm) excitation filter.

To quantify the intracellular lipid accumulation, Huh7 cells were washed in PBS, fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde solution, and then permeabilized with 60% isopropyl alcohol before staining with Oil Red O. Representative microscopic images were obtained on an Olympus IX51 microscope. Intracellular lipids were extracted with isopropyl alcohol, and Oil Red O staining was quantified by measuring the absorbance of the extract at 520 nm and normalized to protein content (Bio-Rad DC protein assay; Bio-Rad, CA, USA).

2.7 Histopathological assessment

H&E and Masson's trichrome-stained paraffin-embedded liver biopsy sections from mice were evaluated by an experienced liver pathologist blinded to the features of the different animal groups. The NAFLD activity score (NAS) and the fibrosis stage were assessed as described elsewhere [20]. Briefly, steatosis was graded as follows: grade 0, <5% of steatotic hepatocytes; grade 1, 5–33%; grade 2, >33–66%; and grade 3, >66%. Lobular inflammation was scored as follows: 0, no foci; 1, 0.5–1 foci; 2, 1–2 foci; and 3, >2 foci. Ballooning was classified as 0, none; 1, few balloon cells; and 2, many balloon cells. In addition, fibrosis staging was defined as 0, none; 1, perisinusoidal and/or pericentral; 2, incomplete central/central bridging fibrosis; 3, complete central/central bridging fibrosis; and 4, definite cirrhosis. NAS was calculated for each liver biopsy based on the sum of scores for steatosis, inflammation and ballooning.

2.8 mRNA isolation and Real Time PCR

qRT-PCRs were performed in the Genomic Facility at Centro de Biología Molecular Severo Ochoa from mouse hepatic samples or from human liver biopsy samples RNA using the SyBr Green method as described in Supplementary Materials where the precise normalization techniques and probe sequences can also be found.

2.9 Data analysis

All data are expressed as mean values \pm SEM and n represents the number of animals. Normal distribution was determined using a Shapiro-Wilk normality test prior to statistical analysis. Whenever normality test was positive, statistical significance was analyzed by using unpaired Student's t test or one- or two-way repeated measures ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's post hoc test. When normality test was not positive, or when significant differences were found between variances (determined by Bartlett's or by F-test of equality of variances), statistical significance was analyzed using Mann Whitney test, unpaired t test with Welch's correction or Kruskal Wallis followed by Dunn's Multiple Comparison Test. Differences were considered statistically significant when P value <0.05.

More information about additional Methods (Electron Microscopy, Mitochondrial Function, ...) can be found in the Supplementary Material.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Reduced GRK2 prevents HFD-induced NAFLD in mice

C57BL/6 mice fed a HFD develop several features of obesity-associated NAFLD [30]. To evaluate the contribution of GRK2 to NAFLD development *in vivo*, we compared the effect of the HFD in the livers of GRK2^{+/-} and WT mice. Hepatic steatosis was detected in WT mice as evidenced by increased liver weight (Fig. 1A), and by histological analysis using H&E as well as Oil Red O staining (Fig. 1B). GRK2^{+/-} livers showed no histologic signs of hepatic steatosis and weighed significantly less than those of HFD-fed WT littermates (Fig. 1A, B). Moreover, the increase in liver TG caused by a HFD was not observed in GRK2^{+/-} mice (Fig. 1C). GRK2 protein levels were increased in WT mice after 12 weeks of HFD, whereas no significant increase was observed in GRK2^{+/-} mice (data not shown) in line with previously reported data [13]. An upregulation of hepatic GRK2 levels was also detected in the *db/db* genetic mice model of obesity both in whole liver lysates and in primary hepatocytes (Fig. S1).

3.2 GRK2 downmodulation protects from non-obese NASH.

We next used the MCD model, one of the best-established models of NASH that causes weight loss rather than weight gain and is not overtly insulin-resistant [31, 32]. WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice were fed either an MCD or a methionine and choline-sufficient equivalent diet (CD) for 4 weeks (Fig. S2 A). The weight loss induced by MCD was equivalent in both genotypes, resulting in a similar body weight at the end of the MCD feeding period (Fig. S2 B). The metabolic assays performed in order to study the glucose tolerance (GTT), insulin resistance (ITT) and gluconeogenic capacity (PTT) showed that GRK2^{+/-} were slightly less affected by the MCD in terms of glucose tolerance and gluconeogenic capacity in the absence of differences in systemic insulin sensitivity (Fig. S2 C, D, E). These results suggest a slightly better preservation of hepatic glycemic handling in GRK2^{+/-} mice in the face of an MCD challenge.

GRK2 protein was markedly upregulated in whole liver lysates of WT mice after 4 weeks of MCD to a similar extent to that found after a HFD, whereas this rise did not occur in GRK2^{+/-} mice (Fig. 2A). This increase occurs specifically in hepatocytes as demonstrated in lysates from primary

cultures of hepatocytes or Kupffer cells isolated from WT mice fed either a CD or an MCD (Fig. 2B).

As expected, MCD caused an increase in the liver-to-body weight ratio (Fig. 3A). However, this indicator of steatosis was significantly lower in GRK2^{+/-} mice. Decreased lipid deposition was found upon histological examination in GRK2^{+/-} livers (Fig. 3B) which also showed a significantly less pronounced increase of TG content after the MCD compared to WT mice (Fig. 3C). This partial protection against hepatic steatosis observed in GRK2^{+/-} mice does not seem to be due to decreased circulating levels of TG or NEFA since no significant differences in these parameters were detected between MCD-fed WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice (Fig. S3).

One major feature of NASH besides steatosis is inflammation. GRK2^{+/-} mice also showed lower macrophage infiltration induced by the MCD with a close to significant difference relative to the WT (Fig. 3D) as assessed by the overall F4/80 immunostained area (normalized by that of fat-free tissue). Moreover, the MCD induced the stimulation of inflammatory pathways such as STAT3 in the liver of WT mice, an effect not observed in GRK2^{+/-} mice (Fig. 3E). We have also detected lower mRNA levels of the pro-inflammatory markers *tnf* (TNF α or tumor necrosis factor alpha), *ccl2* (MCP1) and *icam1* in MCD-fed GRK2^{+/-} mice compared to WT mice. A tendency towards a reduced expression was also observed for *il6* and *il1b* (Fig. 3F), whereas no change was detected in *vcam* mRNA (Fig. S4).

3.3 GRK2^{+/-} mice are protected from the development of the histopathological signs of NASH.

Liver samples from both WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice fed or not an MCD were subjected to a blinded anatomopathological examination in order to assign a NAS [20]. CD-fed mice displayed non-pathological liver histology regardless of the genotype (Table 1). After the MCD feeding, WT mice developed histologic features of NASH with a significantly higher NAS with respect to CD-fed mice including increased steatosis, inflammation and hepatocyte ballooning (Table 1). Conversely, MCD-fed GRK2^{+/-} mice had significantly lower NAS than their WT littermates, including lower grade of steatosis and inflammation as well as absence of ballooning hepatocellular injury, being thus diagnosed of simple steatosis (not NASH) (Table 1).

3.4 Several cellular processes implicated in the development of NASH are differentially affected by an MCD in GRK2^{+/-} mice.

We next characterized the status of hepatic processes such as ER stress, FA metabolism, mitochondrial dynamics and autophagy involved in NASH.

An increased phosphorylation of eIF2 α (eukaryotic translation initiation factor 2alpha) and decreased ERK (extracellular signal-regulated kinases) 1/2 and p38 MAPK activation in response to the MCD,

all related with ER stress in the liver [33, 34], were detected in WT but not observed in GRK2^{+/-} animals (Fig. 4). We also detected a MCD-induced activation of the ATF-6 and JNK branches of the ER stress response in WT mice that was not so clearly observed in GRK2^{+/-} littermates Fig. S5. Also, the expression of PPAR γ , a key transcription factor for the expression of lipogenic genes in the liver, was markedly increased in MCD-fed WT but not in GRK2^{+/-} mice. Similarly, CD36 (cluster of differentiation 36) a transmembrane protein involved in FA import and a key PPAR γ -target gene, was increased after the MCD feeding to a much lesser extent in GRK2^{+/-} compared to WT mice (Fig. 5A). Accordingly, mRNA expression of CD36 was significantly lower in GRK2^{+/-} mice (Fig. S6). On the other hand, fatty acid synthase (FAS), the enzyme that catalyzes the last step of *de novo* lipogenesis (DNL), was decreased upon MCD feeding in both WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice (Fig. 5A).

We also analyzed the levels of OPA (optic atrophy) 1 and mitofusin 2, two markers of mitochondrial fusion, a process with a critical role in alleviating hepatic FA accumulation [35]. Interestingly, the expression of these proteins was significantly reduced in MCD-fed WT but not in GRK2^{+/-} mice (Fig. 6A). Accordingly, the aspect ratio of hepatic mitochondria from GRK2 hemizygous animals indicated a more elongated structure than those from WT mice after the MCD feeding (Fig. 6B). Moreover, mRNA levels of mitochondrial transcription factor A (*tfam*) and of *ppargc1* (Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma coactivator 1-alpha or PGC-1 α), key regulators of mitochondrial biogenesis, and of *coI* (subunit of the mitochondrial respiratory complex) were significantly higher in MCD-fed GRK2^{+/-} than in WT mice (Fig. 6C). However, no apparent changes in mitochondrial respiration were detected between genotypes in isolated mitochondria using the substrates succinate (Fig. 6D) or glutamate-malate (Fig. S7).

Finally, the impairment of the autophagic flux, a key event in the development of NASH [5], was characterized by the accumulation of the p62/SQSTM1 protein observed in the liver of MCD-fed WT mice. GRK2^{+/-} animals did not accumulate p62 and preserved an active autophagy in the face of an MCD, as also demonstrated by the effective conversion of LC3 (microtubule-associated protein 1A/1B-light chain 3) I to LC3 II (Fig. 7A). Moreover, the activation status of autophagy-regulatory pathways was differentially altered: AMPK (AMP-activated protein kinase) phosphorylation was slightly enhanced and that of S6, a readout of the mTORC1 (mammalian target of rapamycin complex 1) autophagy-inhibitory pathway, was reduced in the liver of GRK2^{+/-} (Fig. 7B), indicating a better preservation of autophagy in these animals. Of note, the overall basal levels of markers of ER stress (p-eiF2 α), mitochondrial fusion (OPA1), lipid handling (FAS) or autophagy (p62) do not show any significant difference in the livers of GRK2^{+/-} animals when compared to those from WT

mice (Fig. S8), indicating that reduced expression of GRK2 does not trigger *per se* changes in the expression of the markers of the analyzed cellular processes.

3.5 Hepatic GRK2 levels are increased in biopsies of steatosis and NASH patients and its upregulation fosters lipid accumulation in a human hepatocyte cell line.

In order to investigate changes in GRK2 expression during human NAFLD, we used two independent cohorts of patients from different hospitals to quantify GRK2 protein and mRNA levels. In Cohort 1, we found increased levels of GRK2 mRNA (*adrbk1*) in both SS and NASH biopsies compared to NL (Fig. 8A). GRK2 protein levels were upregulated in SS biopsies compared to NL samples in patients with a body mass index (BMI) below 25 kg/m² (lean subjects) (Fig. 8B). This rise of GRK2 protein levels was also observed in patients with overweight or obesity in SS samples (BMI > 25 kg/m², Fig. 8C) and in NASH patients compared to NL controls (BMI > 25 kg/m², Fig. 8D). Quantification by immunohistochemistry of GRK2-positive area in Cohort 2 showed a statistically significant increase both in SS and NASH liver biopsies compared to NL also using this technique (Fig. 8E and Fig.S9).

In order to establish a direct cause-effect relationship, GRK2 was overexpressed by adeno-associated viral infection in a human hepatoma cell line (Huh7) and these cells were loaded with palmitic acid. As shown in Fig. 8F, GRK2 overexpression was able to increase palmitic acid-induced intracellular lipid accumulation, although overexpression of GRK2 does not cause *per se* such effect. Consistently, preliminary data suggest that *in vivo* GRK2 protein overexpression by adenoviral injection was not able to cause by itself hepatic steatosis (Fig. S10). Overall, these results indicate that there is a parallelism between the levels of GRK2 in hepatocytes and histologic features of NAFLD patients and that GRK2 upregulation is sufficient to foster palmitic acid-induced intracellular lipid accumulation in a human hepatocyte cell line.

4. DISCUSSION

The liver plays a key role in the control of glucose and lipid metabolism and at the same time is a target organ in metabolic disorders such as T2D or obesity. In fact, NAFLD is considered as the hepatic manifestation of the metabolic syndrome. We have previously described that GRK2, widely known for its role in the regulation of GPCRs, plays a role in HFD-induced IR and obesity and that lowering GRK2 levels can reverse an already established insulin-resistant phenotype [9, 14]. In this work, we have used mice fed an MCD, a nutritional model in which the development of NASH is accompanied neither by increased body weight/adiposity nor by IR establishment [31, 32]. Our data

demonstrate that GRK2^{+/-} mice are protected from the development from MCD-dependent NASH and show decreased signs of hepatic steatosis and inflammation, thus establishing that GRK2 downmodulation may prevent or delay the development of NASH.

Several lines of evidence support a role for GRK2 in the establishment and/or development of NASH. First, the expression of GRK2 protein in the liver increases after a HFD feeding [13] and this increase was not observed in other non-steatotic conditions such as aging or TNF α -induced IR. Likewise, an MCD challenge causes a rise in hepatic GRK2 levels, suggesting that this elevation may be more closely connected to fatty liver than to overall changes in the systemic metabolic profile of the mice. Second, the increase of hepatic GRK2 protein levels triggered by either HFD or MCD was not observed in GRK2^{+/-} animals, which are protected from steatosis and full-blown NASH, suggesting that there is a threshold above which the elevation of GRK2 may be linked to the development of hepatic steatosis. Since GRK2^{+/-} animals do not accumulate enough fat, they might not trigger this increase in GRK2 that feeds forward a pathological cycle of worsened lipid handling. Furthermore, GRK2 hepatic protein is increased in two different human cohorts of patients with hepatic steatosis or NASH. Interestingly, this increase of GRK2 levels in human biopsies is detected both in lean and obese individuals, enforcing the notion that GRK2 upregulation is not so much linked to an obese phenotype as it is to fatty liver. Additionally, reduced GRK2 levels correlate with decreased expression of several inflammatory markers (among them cytokines and integrins) and macrophage infiltration after an MCD challenge. Finally, adenoviral-mediated GRK2 overexpression experiments in different systems indicate that increased GRK2 is able to enhance the accumulation of intracellular TG in a human hepatocyte cell line exposed to palmitic acid, and suggest that a metabolic insult or a context of excessive fat supply may be required for GRK2 up-regulation to boost steatosis. Altogether, these results strongly suggest a causal relationship between GRK2 levels in hepatocytes and the ability of these cells to accumulate intracellular lipids, and a link between the amount of GRK2 in the liver and the presence of hepatic steatosis and NASH in mice and humans.

The excessive lipid accumulation caused by the MCD disturbs the function of the ER in hepatocytes, thereby generating an ER stress response that is however unable to alleviate ER stress in the context of a fatty liver. Furthermore, ER stress responses can promote lipid accumulation in hepatocytes that could trigger further ER stress, thus promoting a positive feedback loop [3]. As expected, MCD-fed WT mice present signs of increased ER stress response in each of the three branches of this process (eIF2 α , ATF6 and JNK) or the inactivation of p38 MAPK that has been related with ER stress via regulation of Xbp1 splicing [34]. However, according to these markers, GRK2^{+/-} mice do not seem to mount an equivalent ER stress response probably because of the lack of lipid accumulation in their

livers. Consistently, we found that WT and GRK2^{+/-} animals display differences in hepatic lipid metabolism markers. For instance, PPAR γ promotes lipid storage and is increased in MCD-fed WT mice, as also observed in human steatotic livers [36], but not in MCD-fed GRK2^{+/-} animals. Also, CD36, a PPAR γ -target gene encoding a transmembrane protein regulating FA influx, is more sharply increased by the MCD in WT than in GRK2^{+/-} mice. This fact could promote an increased FA uptake in WT MCD-fed mice that would not take place in GRK2^{+/-} animals. Overall, we can conclude that low GRK2 levels are able to impinge on lipid accumulation in the liver by mechanisms probably involving PPAR γ - and CD36-mediated FA handling.

The excess of FA in the hepatocytes is usually metabolized in the mitochondria, and thus mitochondrial biogenesis and dynamics (fission and fusion events) are important for regulating lipid catabolism under stress conditions [37]. In this regard, we found higher levels of *tfam*, *ppargc1a* and *coI* mRNA in GRK2^{+/-} mice what indicate increased mitochondrial biogenesis in these mice even when no apparent differences are found regarding mitochondrial function *per se*. Also, mitochondrial fusion events have a critical role in alleviating hepatic FA accumulation [35] and a decrease in the key fusion proteins OPA 1 or mitofusin 2 has been related with NAFLD [38]. Such decrease is clearly observed in the livers of WT but not of GRK2^{+/-} mice, in line with previous data using a long-term HFD feeding where GRK2^{+/-} mice also presented increased levels of mitochondrial fusion markers in cardiac tissue [39], and are in agreement with the more elongated mitochondria present in GRK2^{+/-} livers after the MCD. Altogether, these results suggest that GRK2 hemizygous animals preserve mitochondrial fusion events in the face of MCD-induced metabolic disturbance, which could be associated with the increased mitochondrial biogenesis markers observed in these mice [40].

When the amount of FA exceeds the capacity of oxidation by the mitochondria they are re-esterified into TG that can be accumulated in lipid droplets. Activation of autophagy, for instance by pharmacological or genetic means, is able to decrease lipid content in hepatocytes. In fact, one of the features of healthy hepatocytes is that they can upregulate autophagy in response to dietary lipid challenges as a mechanism of defense against lipotoxicity [41], while during NAFLD there is an impairment of the autophagic flux in these cells[5, 42]. Coherently, in MCD-fed WT mice we found a decrease of autophagic markers while MCD-fed GRK2^{+/-} mice maintained an active autophagy, as demonstrated by the lack of accumulation of p62, the increased conversion of LC3 I to LC3 II, the increased activation of AMPK and the decreased phosphorylation of S6, demonstrating that GRK2^{+/-} mice are protected from the impairment of the autophagic response upon an MCD feeding.

Overall, our data show a pleiotropic protective effect of decreasing GRK2 levels in the modulation of several processes that converge in the amelioration of hepatic steatosis and NASH independently of IR and excessive fat mass accretion. The fact that a reduction in GRK2 is able to prevent steatosis and inflammation, and ameliorate MCD-induced NASH (in addition to preserving insulin sensitivity within the liver under different IR-promoting conditions), further highlights GRK2 as a potential target for the treatment of obese and non-obese NASH particularly since GRK2-hemizygous mice would *bona fide* mimic the effect of the systemic administration of a pharmacological inhibitor for GRK2. NASH and IR usually coexist in the human pathology and appear together with other comorbidities such as cardiovascular disease, in which GRK2 downmodulation plays a beneficial role [15]. Therefore, targeting GRK2 could promote distinct beneficial effects in multiple tissues resulting in an improvement of the different pathological effects linked to the metabolic syndrome.

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FIGURE LEGENDS:

Figure 1. Decreased GRK2 levels protects mice from HFD-induced hepatic steatosis. WT and GRK2 hemizygous (GRK2^{+/-}) mice were fed a HFD for 12 weeks. (A) Bar graph of the liver weight of WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice after either SD or HFD feeding. (B) Liver sections from SD and HFD-fed WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice stained with Oil Red O and H&E. Representative photomicrographs are shown (magnification $\times 40$; scale bar 10 μm and $\times 10$; scale bar 0.1 mm, respectively). (C) Hepatic TG were extracted, measured and expressed as equivalent triolein concentration (mg/ml) and normalized by mg of tissue. The increase in TG content in the liver caused by the HFD is shown. Data are means \pm SEM of 4-6 animals per group. Statistical significance was analyzed by unpaired t-test (C) or one-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's post-test (A). *P < 0.05; **P < 0.01; ***P < 0.005.

Figure 2. In MCD-induced NASH GRK2 protein levels are increased in the liver of wild-type, but not in GRK2^{+/-} mice, and this rise is specifically detected in hepatocytes. (A) GRK2 protein levels were detected by Western blot in whole liver lysates from WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice fed an MCD for 4 weeks. (B) Primary hepatocytes or Kupffer cells were isolated from WT mice fed either CD or MCD and lysates immunoblotted for GRK2. GRK2 protein levels were quantitated by densitometric analysis and normalized by GAPDH or β -actin loading controls. Data are means \pm SEM of 4-7 animals per group. Statistical significance was analyzed by unpaired t-test or Mann-Whitney test, depending on the normal distribution of the data. *P < 0.05; **P < 0.01; ***P < 0.005. Representative immunoblots are shown.

Figure 3. GRK2 downmodulation limits hepatic lipid accumulation and inflammation in the face of an MCD intervention. (A) Bar graph of the liver weight of WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice after 4 weeks of CD or MCD normalized by body weight. (B) Representative photomicrographs of liver sections from MCD-fed WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice stained with Oil Red O and H&E (magnification $\times 40$; scale bar 10 μm and $\times 10$; scale bar 0.1 mm, respectively). (C) Hepatic TG were quantitated as in Fig. 1C. The increase in TG content in the liver caused by the MCD is shown. (D) Representative photomicrographs showing the immunohistochemical analysis of liver sections using the F4/80 antibody macrophage marker and counterstained with hematoxylin (magnification $\times 20$; scale bar 0.1 mm). Positively stained area was quantified using Image J Software and normalized by fat-free tissue area. (E) Liver lysates from CD and MCD fed WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice were probed with antibodies against the phosphorylated and total form of STAT3 (Tyr705). Representative immunoblots and densitometric analysis are shown (F) Hepatic expression of mRNA encoding *tnf*, *ccl2*, *il6*, *il1b* and *icam1* was measured by qPCR. Data are means \pm SEM of 4-7 animals per group. Statistical significance was analyzed by unpaired t-test (C,D,F) or one-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni's post-test (A,E). *P < 0.05; **P < 0.01; ***P < 0.005.

Table 1. GRK2^{+/-} mice are protected against the development of MCD-induced NASH according to histopathological analysis. NAS (calculated from individual scores for steatosis plus lobular inflammation and ballooning) was assessed by blinded anatomopathological examination of liver sections from WT and

GRK2^{+/-} mice fed either CD or MCD. Statistical significance was analyzed by unpaired t-test or Mann-Whitney test, depending on the normal distribution of the data. Asterisks depict differences between WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice and number signs between CD and MCD. *P<0.05 WT vs GRK2^{+/-}, #P<0.05 CD vs MCD, n=4-7 per group.

Figure 4. The ER stress response triggered by the MCD challenge in wild-type mice is not observed in GRK2^{+/-} animals. Liver lysates from CD and MCD-fed WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice were subjected to Western blot and probed for phosphorylated and total eIF2 α (Ser51), ERK1/2 (Thr202/Tyr204) and p38 MAPK (Thr180/Tyr182). Representative immunoblots and densitometric analysis are shown. Data are means \pm SEM of 4-7 animals per group. Statistical significance was analyzed by unpaired t-test or Mann-Whitney test, depending on the normal distribution of the data. **P < 0.01; ***P<0.005.

Figure 5. Lipid metabolism markers are differentially altered in MCD-fed WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice. (A) Liver lysates from CD and MCD fed WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice were subjected to Western blot and probed with antibodies against PPAR γ , CD36, FAS and GAPDH (loading control). Data are means \pm SEM of 4-7 animals per group. Representative immunoblots and densitometric analysis are shown. Statistical significance was analyzed by unpaired t-test or Mann-Whitney test, depending on the normal distribution of the data. **P < 0.01; ***P<0.005.

Figure 6. Fusion and biogenesis markers, structure and function of mitochondria in MCD-fed WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice (A) Protein levels of OPA1, mitofusin 2 and GAPDH and β -actin (loading controls) were analyzed by Western blot in liver lysates from CD and MCD-fed WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice. Representative immunoblots and densitometric analysis are shown. Data are means \pm SEM of 4-7 animals per group. (B) Representative electron microscopy images of liver sections from MCD-fed WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice are shown (magnification \times 5000; scale bar 500nm); aspect ratio of liver mitochondria was analyzed using ImageJ software. Data are means \pm SEM of 3 animals per group. (C) Hepatic expression of mRNA encoding the mitochondrial biogenesis regulator *tfam*, *ppargc1a* and *col* were measured by qPCR. Data are means \pm SEM of 4-7 animals per group. (D) Polarographic profiles of isolated liver mitochondria from MCD-fed control (WT, upper trace) and GRK2^{+/-} (lower trace) animals. The effect of 10mM succinate, 0.5 mM ADP, 5 μ M oligomycin (OL), 5 μ M FCCP and 1 μ M antimycin (Ant A) is shown. Histograms reveal no significant changes in State IV, State III, pseudo-state IV, FCCP-sensible (Uncoupled State III) and inhibited respiration in mitochondria of GRK2^{+/-} mice (gray bars) when compared to controls (WT, open bars). Bars are the mean \pm SEM of 9 determinations from 3 different animals per condition. Statistical significance was analyzed by unpaired t-test or Mann-Whitney test, depending on the normal distribution of the data. *P < 0.05; **P < 0.01; ***P<0.005.

Figure 7. Autophagy is better preserved in the liver of GRK2^{+/-} mice in the face of a MCD-induced NASH. Liver lysates from CD and MCD-fed WT and GRK2^{+/-} mice were subjected to Western blot and probed with antibodies against p62, GAPDH and LC3 I/II (A) and phosphorylated and total AMPK (Thr172) and S6 (Ser240/244) (B). Representative immunoblots and densitometric analysis are shown. Data are means

± SEM of 4-7 animals per group. Results are expressed as fold increase over CD (A) or WT (B). Statistical significance was analyzed by unpaired t-test or Mann-Whitney test, depending on the normal distribution of the data. *P < 0.05; **P < 0.01.

Figure 8. GRK2 levels are upregulated in biopsies of NAFLD patients and GRK2 overexpression increases lipid accumulation after palmitic acid exposure in human hepatoma cells. (A) mRNA was extracted from liver biopsies from individuals with histologically normal liver (NL) or patients with simple steatosis (SS) or NASH belonging to Cohort 1 (see Methods section). qPCR was used to study the levels of mRNA expression of *adrbk1* in these biopsies. Results were normalized with *36b4* mRNA expression. (B to D) Liver biopsies from individuals with histologically normal liver (NL) or patients with simple steatosis (SS) either lean (B) or with BMI >25 kg/m² (C) and from patients with NASH or NL (D) belonging to Cohort 1 were subjected to Western blot and probed with antibodies against GRK2 and tubulin. Densitometric analysis and representative immunoblots are shown. (E) Immunohistochemistry of GRK2 was performed in liver biopsies of patients with SS and NASH and individuals with NL belonging to Cohort 2. GRK2-stained area was quantified. Representative photomicrographs are shown (magnification ×40; scale bar 50 μm). Data are means ± SEM of the specified individuals per group. Statistical significance was analyzed by unpaired t-test or Mann-Whitney test, depending on the normal distribution of the data (B to D) or one-way ANOVA followed by Dunn's post-test (A and E). *P < 0.05; **P < 0.01. (F) Human hepatoma cells (Huh7) were infected with control or GRK2 adeno-associated virus, treated with palmitic acid for 24 hours, and the lipid content was measured by Oil Red O elution. The increase in absorbance caused by the treatment is represented. Representative photomicrographs are shown. The overexpression of GRK2 was confirmed by Western blot. Data are means ± SEM of 5 independent experiments. Statistical significance was analyzed by Bonferroni's post-test (B). *P < 0.05; **P < 0.01.

Table 1.

Diet and genotype		Steatosis	Inflammation	Ballooning	NAS	Diagnosis
CD	WT	0	0	0	0	Normal liver
	GRK2+/-	0.5±0.3	0.25±0.29	0	0.75±0.55	Not NASH (simple steatosis)
MCD	WT	3 ^{###}	1 ^{###}	0.29±0.20	4.29±0.20 ^{###}	Borderline NASH
	GRK2+/-	1.8±0.22 ^{***##}	0.4±0.27	0	2.2±0.42 ^{*#}	Not NASH (simple steatosis)

Figure 1

A

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

A

Figure 6

A

Figure 7

A

Figure 8